

Consumption Behavior of Halal Cosmetic Products: The Mediating Role of Trust on the Effect of Halal Certification on Purchase Intention

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ABSTRACT: Halal certification is still no guarantee that consumers will purchase the product. This study aims to analyze the role of consumer trust in mediating the relationship between halal certification and intentions, where intentions ultimately impact the consumption behavior of halal cosmetic products during the Covid-19 pandemic. The population of this study is the female population in Jakarta aged 15-60 years. The number of research samples to be taken is 160 respondents with the purposive sampling technique. Data will be collected using questionnaires and analyzed using Partial Least Square (PLS) analysis method. Based on the research results, halal certification positively affects consumer trust, and trust has a positive influence on consumer intentions to buy halal products. Halal certification also positively influences consumer intentions to buy halal products. In addition to direct influence, halal certification indirectly affects intentions—the effect of halal certification on intentions through trust mediation. Furthermore, intention positively influences the consumption behavior of halal products.

KEYWORDS: Halal Certification; Trust; Intention; Behavior; Halal Cosmetics

I. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 virus outbreak provides several lessons. One of them is that every violation of Islamic Sharia will cause harm, damage, and destruction (Rifa'i et al., 2020). As a country with the largest Muslim population globally, Muslims can give their best role through the halal industry. The halal industry is in the spotlight during a new normal era when hygiene is the current priority. The potential is getting more prominent along with the new normal order, which prioritizes cleanliness or hygiene (Kamila, 2020).

Halal means permitted or based on Islamic law, which refers to products permitted for consumption by Muslims (Ambali & Bakar, 2013). The concept of halal emphasizes cleanliness, safety, process, manufacture, and production on a good platform in Islam (Hussain et al., 2016). Halal products are products that are declared halal by the provisions of Islamic law (Kamila, 2020). The product categories included in halal products are food and beverages and cosmetics and personal care, pharmacy, tourism, and hospitality (Islam & Chandrasekaran, 2015).

One of the halal product categories is cosmetics and personal care. Cosmetic and personal care products are considered halal only when all ingredients meet halal and sharia requirements and haram materials such as alcohol and ingredients derived from pork are not used in their manufacture, and all ingredients must be produced, stored, packaged, and shipped according to halal standards (Islam & Chandrasekaran, 2015). Before the Covid-19 pandemic in 2019, Indonesia was in the second position (\$ 4 billion) after India (\$ 6 billion) in the halal cosmetics shopping market. Muslim spending from 1.9 Billion Muslims on cosmetics globally in 2019 also increased compared to 2018, namely to \$ 66 billion, with India, Indonesia, and Russia representing the top three countries by expenditure (DinarStandard, 2020).

The Covid-19 pandemic has an impact on decreasing public consumption activities which have started to occur in all products, including halal cosmetic products (Sumarni, 2020). The Covid-19 pandemic has significantly impacted beauty products and cosmetics sales, especially make-up because many consumers are forced to live and work from home. Given the profound and widespread impact of Covid-19, global Muslim consumer spending on cosmetics is expected to fall by 2.5% to \$ 64 billion by 2020 (DinarStandard, 2020).

Consuming halal products is an obligation for Muslims. Therefore, halal cosmetic manufacturers are trying to obtain halal certification so that Muslims can easily accept their products. Consumers see product quality assurance through the existence of

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halal certification. Halal certification, whether in the form of a certificate, logo, trademark, or stamp, is a guarantee that the product has gone through a rigorous and extensive inspection by a legitimate Islamic certification authority and shows that the source, material, and process are based on Sharia principles (Al-Mazeedi et al., 2013; Nawi & Nasir, 2014).

Consumers will only trust halal products if a halal certification (Bakar et al., 2017). The finding also consistent with the findings of Omar et al., (2012), where there is no other way how a consumer can determine the halalness of a product except by relying on a credible halal logo. Halal product manufacturers include halal certification to increase consumer trust (Rahman et al., 2015). Halal certification has a positive and significant effect on consumer trust (Novagusda & Deriawan, 2019; Yusuf et al., 2019). Halal certification is proven to increase consumer trust in halal products (Mangkarto, 2005). Halal certification also has a positive and significant effect on the intention to buy halal products (Faturohman, 2019; Fitria et al., 2019; Majid et al., 2015; Nurhasanah & Hariyani, 2017). Halal certification provides quality assurance assessed by consumers and leads to broader acceptance of products (Rajagopal et al., 2011). However, halal certification was also found to have no significant effect on buying intention in halal products (Putri & Rimadias, 2020; Setiawan & Mauluddi, 2020). This means that halal certification has not been guaranteed to be a factor that significantly influences intention in buying a product.

Meanwhile, consumers usually buy products with the halal logo printed on the packaging and trust the producers wholeheartedly (Alqudsi, 2014). This shows the validity of consumers' trust in the product's halal status (Aziz & Vui, 2012). Based on the Commitment-Trust Theory of Relationship Marketing, trust plays an essential role in instilling consumer trust and creating commitments considered important in purchasing behavior (Morgan & Hunt, 1994). Thus, trust can mediate the effect of halal certification on purchase intention. Zakaria et al., (2015) show that trust plays a role in mediating the relationship between halal certification and intention.

Trust in halal product producers is essential to shape consumer intentions and behavior. This is based on consumers' preference to buy products from trusted brands and well-known manufacturers (Ismail et al., 2019). Trust has a positive and significant effect on buying intention in halal products (Handriana et al., 2020; Romle et al., 2016; Triantoro et al., 2020). However, Setiawan & Mauluddi, (2020) show that consumer trust does not significantly affect the intention to buy halal products. This means that consumer trust has not been guaranteed to be a factor that significantly influences the intention to buy halal products.

Futhermore, the intention will influence consumption behavior. Intention would depict the people's plans and motivations to purchase a product in the near future (Wibowo et al., 2020). Intention positively affects the consumption behavior of halal products (Huda et al., 2018; Kadengkang & Linarti, 2020; Khan et al., 2017). However, Ma'rifat et al., (2015) show that intention has a negative and significant effect on the consumption behavior of halal products. This means that the intention can reduce the consumption behavior of a halal product.

Based on the description above, findings show that halal certification does not significantly affect purchase intentions, even though halal cosmetic manufacturers are trying to obtain it so that Muslims can easily accept their products. This shows the validity of consumers' trust in the product's halal status. Therefore, seeing the effect of halal certification on intention through trust is essential where in turn, the intention will impact the behavior of consuming halal products. By the main focus of Theory of Planned Behavior (Ajzen, 1985) namely the individual's intention to perform certain behaviors, many factors have influenced the stability of behavioral intentions.

Research on the consumption behavior of halal products is important because halal cosmetic manufacturers are trying to obtain halal certification so that Muslims can easily accept their products. In addition, the majority of Indonesia's population is Muslim, plus the emergence of halal issues during the Covid-19 pandemic. The halal products that focus on this research are cosmetic products and halal personal care from local brands in Indonesia.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB)

The Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) has proven to be the best way of predicting individual consumption intentions (Ajzen, 1991). In addition, TPB provides a socio-psychological framework for understanding and predicting the determinants of human behavior and integrating several fundamental concepts in the social and behavioral sciences (Armitage & Conner, 2000). TPB is a conventional model helpful in predicting consumer buying behavior (Bashir et al., 2019).

Behavior

Kotler & Keller, (2012) define consumer behavior as the study of how a person chooses to buy uses or no longer uses goods, services, ideas, or experiences to fulfill their needs and desires. Consumer behavior also means a reflection of

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consumer decision-making and the physical activity that a person does when evaluating, obtaining, using, or not an item and service (Shamser, 2016). Their buying intention will first influence a person's buying behavior before the purchase decision is actually implemented (Ajzen, 1985).

The theory of consumer behavior built on Islamic sharia is different from conventional theories. The primary differences are related to the fundamental values that form the basis of theory, motives, and consumption goals to budget allocations (Huda et al., 2018). The consumption behavior of halal products can be reflected through the regular use of halal products, routine purchases of halal products, purchases of halal products compared to non-halal products, large budget allocations in purchasing halal products (Adiba, 2019).

Halal Certification and Trust

Halal certification identifies that the product meets halal requirements (Razalli et al., 2013). Halal product manufacturers include halal certification to increase consumer trust (Rahman et al., 2015). Halal certification has a positive and significant effect on consumer trust (Novagusda & Deriawan, 2019). The higher consumer perception regarding halal certification impacts increasing consumer trust to buy halal products. Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H1 = Halal certification has a positive and significant effect on trust.

Trust and Intention

Trust in halal product manufacturers is essential to shape consumer intentions and behavior. This is based on consumers' preference to buy products from trusted brands and well-known manufacturers (Ismail et al., 2019). Consumer trust has been shown to positively and significantly affect buying intention in halal products (Handriana et al., 2020; Romle et al., 2016; Triantoro et al., 2020). The existence of a high level of trust from consumers impacts increasing their intention to buy halal products. Buying intention is the stage where consumers form their choice among several brands that are incorporated in the device of choice, then ultimately make a purchase on the most preferred alternative or the process where consumers buy an item or service based on various considerations (Septianti et al., 2021). Trust becomes a consumer action to depend on the integrity of the product provider accompanied by positive expectations and perceptions from consumers so that the individual will then use halal products (Nurachmi & Setiawan, 2020).

Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H2 = Trust has a positive and significant effect on buying intention in halal products.

Halal Certification and Intention

Halal certification provides quality assurance that is valued by consumers and leads to broader product acceptance (Rajagopal et al., 2011). Halal certification has been shown to positively and significantly affect buying intention in halal products (Faturahman, 2019; Fitria et al., 2019; Majid et al., 2015; Nurhasanah & Hariyani, 2017). The higher the consumer's perception of the halal certification of a product, the higher the consumer in buying intention in halal products.

Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H3 = Halal certification has a positive and significant effect on buying intention in halal products.

Halal Certification, Trust and Intention

Halal certification is used to inform and convince consumers that the product is halal and sharia-compliant (Shafie & Othman, 2006). However, halal certification was found to have no significant effect on intention in buying halal products (Putri & Rimadiaz, 2020; Setiawan & Mauluddi, 2020). Trust can mediate the effect of halal certification on buying intention. Zakaria et al. (2015) show that trust acts as a mediator between the relationship between halal certification and buying intention. Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H4 = Trust mediates the effect of halal certification on intention in buying halal products.

Intention and Behavior

Ajzen, (1985) argues that human behavior is first influenced by intention (behavior intention). Thus, a person's buying behavior will be influenced by buying intention before the purchase decision is actually implemented. Intentions have a positive and significant effect on the consumption behavior of halal products (Huda et al., 2018; Kadengkang & Linarti, 2020; Khan et al., 2017). The higher a person's intention towards halal products, the higher the consumption behavior.

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Based on the description above, the following hypothesis can be formulated:

H5 = Intention has a positive and significant effect on the consumption behavior of halal products.

Based on the hypothesis development, this study's framework (research model) is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Research Model

III. METHOD

Type of Research

This research is causal research, which explains the effect of independent variables on the dependent variable. The variables to be used consist of halal certification, trust, intention, and behavior. Measuring variables in this study will use a Likert scale where the latent variables to be measured are translated into indicators. Then these indicators are used as a starting point for compiling instrument items (questionnaires) which can be in the form of statements or questions (Sekaran & Bougie, 2016). This study will use a Likert scale with a range of categories 1-7, namely 1 = strongly disagree; 2 = disagree; 3 = quite disagree; 4 = neutral; 5 = quite agree; 6 = agree; 7 = totally agree.

Variables

Latents	Indicators	References
Halal Certification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • knowledge of halal certification bodies (HC1), • the inclusion of the halal logo on product packaging (HC2), • product content according to halal certification (HC3). 	(Aziz & Chok, 2013)
Trust	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • product performance that meets expectations (TR1), • the product can be trusted (TR2), • the product is reliable (TR3), • product confidence (TR4). 	(Handriana et al., 2020)
Intention	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Interest in buying halal products (IN1) • main preference on halal products (IN2), • tendency to refer products to others (IN3) • tendency to always seek information about products of interest (IN4). 	(Haro, 2018)
Behavior	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the routine use of halal products (BV1), • routine purchases of halal products (BV2), • purchases of halal products compared to non-halal products (BV3), • significant budget allocations in purchasing halal products (BV4). 	(Adiba, 2019)

Population and Sample

The population of this study is Jakarta residents who are female and aged 15-60 years, where the data in 2020 amounted to 3.304.885 people (BPS-Statistics of DKI Jakarta Province, 2020). Due to the absence of a complete sampling frame, this study uses a non-probability sampling technique, namely purposive sampling, with the respondent's criteria (1) being Muslim (2) having bought and used local brands of halal cosmetics and personal care products at least once. In the absence of a complete sampling frame and the method of analysis to be used is SEM analysis, this number of studies requires a sample of at least five times the number of parameters to be analyzed (Ferdinand, 2014). This study requires a sample of at least five times 16 indicators, namely 90 respondents. However, considering many women in Jakarta, the target number of respondents in this study was 160 (10 times 16 indicators).

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Analysis Method

This research use component/variance-based structural. Component/variance based structural equation modeling is an alternative to covariance-based SEM known as partial least square (PLS). SEM-PLS consists of measurement and structural models (Ghozali & Latan, 2015).

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Evaluation of Measurement Model (Outer Model)

Evaluation of the measurement model can be seen from convergent validity results. Convergent validity is seen from the value of the outer loading. The value of the outer loading indicator, which is more significant than 0.7, is valid. But the value of outer loading which is greater than 0.6 still tolerated for exploratory study. The value of the outer loading of this study can be seen in Figure 2.

Figure 2: The Values of Outer Loading

Based on Figure 2, all indicator variables have an outer loading value greater than 0.6. It means all indicators are valid. It can be concluded that the construct has good convergent validity. The other evaluation of the measurement model is seen in reliability and construct validity results. The reliability of a construct can be seen from the value of Composite Reliability and Cronbach's Alpha.

The construct validity is seen from Average Variance Extracted (AVE) value. It compares the square root value of AVE with the correlation between respective latent constructs in the model. Constructs have good reliability if the Composite Reliability value is more significant than 0.8 and the value of Cronbach's Alpha is more significant than 0.7. The values of Composite Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, and Average Variance Extracted (AVE) can be seen in Table 3.

Table 3: The Values of Composite Reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, Average Variance Extracted (AVE)

	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability	Average Variance Extracted (AVE)
Behavior	0.853	0.901	0.695
Halal Certification	0.759	0.864	0.682
Intention	0.808	0.873	0.635
Trust	0.918	0.942	0.803

Based on Table 3, all constructs are valid. This can be seen from all constructs that have AVE values above 0.5. All constructs are reliable. This is because all constructs must have Composite Reliability values, which are more significant than 0.7. The values of Cronbach's Alpha are more significant than 0.7.

The following evaluation of construct validity is discriminant validity by comparing the square root values of AVE with the correlation between the respective latent constructs. If the AVE square root value of each construct is greater than the correlation between constructs, the model has good discriminant validity. The comparison of AVE

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square root values with inter-construct correlations can be seen through The Fornell-Larcker Criterion (see Table 4).

Table 4: The Fornell-Larcker Criterion

	Behavior	Halal Certification	Intention	Trust
Behavior	0.834			
Halal Certification	0.612	0.826		
Intention	0.716	0.632	0.797	
Trust	0.604	0.571	0.478	0.896

The Fornell-Larcker Criterion shows that the diagonal value in bold is the square root of AVE, while other values are the correlations between the respective latent construct. The discriminant validity is achieved when a diagonal value (in bold) is higher than its row and column values. It can be concluded that discriminant validity for all constructs is achieved (Table 4).

Evaluation of Structural Model (Inner Model)

Evaluation of the structural model looks at the relationship between constructs and the significance values indicated by the value of T-statistics based on PLS output. The coefficient path that has a T-statistic value ≥ 1.654 is significant. The path coefficient can be seen in Table 5.

Table 5: Path Coefficient

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics	P Values	Results
Halal Certification -> Intention	0.532	5.848	0.000	Significant
Halal Certification -> Trust	0.571	8.150	0.000	Significant
Intention -> Behavior	0.716	15.410	0.000	Significant
Trust -> Intention	0.174	2.299	0.011	Significant

Based on Table 11, the direct relationship test between constructs shows that the image construct of halal certification has a positive effect on trust with a parameter coefficient value of 0.571 and is significant because the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the T-statistics value is $> T\text{-table}$ ($8.150 > 1.654$). The trust construct has a positive effect on intention with the parameter coefficient value of 0.174 and significant because the p-value is $0.011 < 0.05$ and the T-statistics value is $> T\text{-table}$ ($2.299 > 1.654$). The halal certification construct has a positive effect on intentions with a parameter coefficient value of 0.532 and significant because the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the T-statistics value is $< T\text{-table}$ ($5,848 > 1.654$). The intention construct has a positive effect on behavior with the parameter coefficient value of 0.716 and is significant because the p-value is $0.000 < 0.05$ and the T-statistics value is $> T\text{-table}$ ($15,410 > 1.654$). Thus, H1, H2, H3, and H5 are accepted.

In addition to the direct effect, the indirect effect can be seen in Table 8. In this study, the indirect effect seen is the effect of halal certification on intentions through trust.

Table 6: Specific Indirect Effects

	Original Sample (O)	T Statistics	P Values	Results
Halal Certification -> Trust -> Intention	0.099	2.017	0.022	Significant

Based on Table 6, the effect of halal certification on intentions through trust is 0.099. This indirect effect is positive and significant because the p-value is $0.022 < 0.05$ and the T-statistics value is $> T\text{-table}$ ($2.017 > 1.654$). Thus, H4 is accepted. Evaluation of the structural model is also done by looking at the value of R-Square. The value of R-Square shows the variability of the model that the constructs can explain in the model. The R-Square value of the results of this study can be seen in Table 7.

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Table 7: R-Square

	R-Square
Behavior	0.513
Intention	0.420
Trust	0.326

Based on Table 7, the R-Square value of trust is 0.326, which means that the variability of the construct of trust in halal products that the construct of halal certification can explain is 32.60%. In contrast, other variables outside the model explain the remaining 67.40%. The value of R-Square of intention is 0.420, which means that the variability of the construct of intention that can be explained by the construct of halal certification and trust is 42.00%. In comparison, other variables outside the model explain the remaining 58.00%. The behavioral R Square value of 0.513 means that the variability of the behavioral construct that can be explained by the intention construct is 51.30%, while other variables outside the model explain the remaining 48.70%.

Evaluation of the structural model is also done by looking at the value of F Square. F Square assesses the effect size model (Table 10). In addition to evaluating the R Square values of all endogenous constructs, the change in the R Square values when certain exogenous constructs are eliminated from the model can be used to evaluate whether if any constructs are omitted it can have a substantive impact on the endogenous constructs.

Table 8. F-Square

	Behavior	Halal Certification	Intention	Trust
Behavior				
Halal Certification			0.329	0.484
Intention	1.053			
Trust			0.035	

The effect size value of halal certification on trust is 0.484 (large). The effect size value of halal certification on intention is 0.329 (large). The value of the effect size of trust on intention is 0.035 (low). The value of the effect size of the intention on behavior is 1.058 (high).

Evaluation of the structural model is also seen through the value of Q-Square. The value of Q-Square is used to measure how well the observed values generated by the model and its parameter estimates are. The value of Q-Square > 0 indicates that the model has predictive relevance. The magnitude of the value of Q-Square has a range of $0 < Q\text{-Square} < 1$ where the closer to 1 the predictive relevance of the model is getting better. The following is the Q-Square value from the blindfolding menu for the results of this study which can be seen in Table 9.

Table 9. Q-Square

	SSO	SSE	Q ² (=1-SSE/SSO)
Behavior	640.000	427.549	0.332
Halal Certification	480.000	480.000	
Intention	640.000	481.575	0.248
Trust	640.000	486.470	0.240

The Q-Square values of belief, intention and behavior are 0.240, 0.248 and 0.332, respectively. The three values of Q-Square are greater than 0 so that it shows evidence that the observed values have been reconstructed properly so that the model has predictive relevance.

The Effect of Halal Certification on Consumer Trust

Halal certification has a positive effect on consumer trust. The effect of halal certification on consumer trust is proven to be significant. This shows that halal certification affects consumer trust in halal cosmetic products. The higher consumer perception regarding halal certification impacts increasing consumer trust to buy halal cosmetic products.

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The results of this study are consistent with the research results by Novagusda & Deriawan, (2019) and Yusuf et al., (2019), which shows that halal certification has a positive and significant effect on consumer trust. The existence of halal certification impacts increasing consumer trust to buy halal products. This is because halal certification identifies that the product meets halal requirements (Razalli et al., 2013). Halal product manufacturers include halal certification to increase consumer trust (Rahman et al., 2015).

In this study, halal certification is reflected through knowledge of halal certification bodies (HC1), the inclusion of the halal logo on product packaging (HC2), and product content according to halal certification (HC3). The inclusion of a halal logo on product packaging and information on product content according to halal certification are the two indicators that contribute the most to the measurement of halal certification. Consumers feel that the inclusion of a halal logo on product packaging and information on product content according to halal certification shows that the product has been certified halal.

The Effect of Trust on Intention

Trust has a positive influence on consumer intentions to buy halal products. The effect of trust on consumer intentions is proven to be significant. This shows that trust affects consumers' intentions to buy halal cosmetic products. The higher the trust in halal cosmetic products, the higher the purchase intention for halal cosmetic products.

The results of this study are consistent with the results of research by Handriana et al., (2020); Romle et al., (2016); Triantoro et al., (2020), which show that trust has a positive and significant effect on the purchase intention of halal products. The higher the trust in halal products, the higher the purchase intention.

In this study, trust is reflected through product performance that meets expectations (TR1), the product can be trusted (TR2), the product is reliable (TR3), and product confidence (TR4). Trustworthy products are the indicators that contribute the most to measuring trust. Consumers feel that the product's perception can be trusted shows their trust in halal products. Consumers will feel calm if the product purchased can be trusted in halal (Bakar et al., 2017).

Effect of Halal Certification on Intention

Halal certification has a positive influence on consumer intentions to buy halal products. The effect of halal certification on consumer intentions is proven to be significant. This shows that halal certification affects consumers' intentions to buy halal cosmetic products. The higher consumer perception regarding halal certification impacts increasing consumer intention to buy halal cosmetic products.

The results of this study are consistent with the results of research by Faturohman, (2019); Fitria et al., (2019); Majid et al., (2015); Nurhasanah & Hariyani, (2017), which show that halal certification has proven to have a positive and significant effect on buying intention in halal products. The higher the consumer's perception of the halal certification of a product, the higher the buying intention in halal products. This is because halal certification provides quality assurance valued by consumers and leads to broader product acceptance (Rajagopal et al., 2011).

In this study, halal certification is reflected through knowledge of halal certification bodies (HC1), the inclusion of the halal logo on product packaging (HC2), and product content according to halal certification (HC3). The inclusion of a halal logo on product packaging and information on product content according to halal certification are the two indicators that contribute the most to the measurement of halal certification. Consumers feel that the inclusion of a halal logo on product packaging and information on product content according to halal certification shows that the product has been certified halal.

The Effect of Halal Certification on Intentions through Trust

Halal certification positively influences consumer intentions to buy halal products through trust. The effect of halal certification on intentions through trust is proven to be significant. This shows that halal certification indirectly influences consumers' intentions to buy halal cosmetic products through trust.

The results of this study indicate that the effect of halal certification on buying intention can be mediated by trust. Zakaria et al., (2015) show that trust acts as a mediator between the relationship between halal certification and buying intention. Halal certification is used to inform and convince consumers that the product is halal and sharia-compliant (Shafie & Othman, 2006).

Halal certification can build consumer trust to not hesitate to buy products (Yusuf et al., 2019). Based on the Commitment-Trust Theory of Relationship Marketing, trust plays an essential role in instilling consumer trust and

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creating commitment considered necessary in purchasing behavior (Morgan & Hunt, 1994). This shows the validity among consumers of the belief in the product's halal status (Aziz & Vui, 2012).

The Effect of Intentions on Consumption Behavior of Halal Products

Intentions have a positive influence on the consumption behavior of halal products. The effect of intention on the consumption behavior of halal products is proven to be significant. This shows that the higher the consumer's intention to buy halal cosmetic products, the higher the consumer behavior in consuming halal cosmetic products.

The results of this study are consistent with the results of research by Huda et al., (2018); Kadengkang & Linarti, (2020); Khan et al., (2017), which shows that intention has a positive and significant effect on the consumption behavior of halal products. The higher the intention towards halal products, the higher the consumption behavior.

In this study, consumption behavior is reflected through the routine use of halal products (BV1), routine purchases of halal products (BV2), purchases of halal products compared to non-halal products (BV3), and significant budget allocations in purchasing halal products (BV4). The purchase of halal products compared to non-halal products is the indicator that contributes the most in measuring consumption behavior. Consumers feel that when they buy halal products compared to non-halal products, they already have the behavior to buy and consume halal products.

V. CONCLUSIONS

Halal certification has a positive effect on consumer trust. The higher consumer perception regarding halal certification impacts increasing consumer trust to buy halal products. Trust has a positive influence on consumer intentions to buy halal products. The higher the trust in halal cosmetic products, the higher the purchase intention for halal cosmetic products. Halal certification also positively influences consumer intentions to buy halal products. The higher consumer perception regarding halal certification impacts increasing consumer intention to buy halal cosmetic products. In addition to direct influence, Halal certification has an indirect effect on intentions. Halal certification has a positive indirect effect on intentions through trust. In the future, intention positively influences the consumption behavior of halal products. The higher the consumer's intention to buy halal cosmetic products, the higher the consumer behavior in consuming halal cosmetic products.

Implication

The results of this study can be used by local cosmetic companies or producers in Indonesia as a reference in business activities through a study of consumer behavior related to consumer trust in the consumption behavior of halal cosmetic products. Related to the implications of the halal certification variable, companies can increase the perception of halal certification by including a halal logo on cosmetic product packaging and information on the content of cosmetic products according to halal certification. Regarding the implications of the trust variable, the company can show that the product is a trustworthy cosmetic product. Related to the implications of the intention variable, companies can notice that consumers tend always to seek information about halal cosmetic products. Related to the implications of behavioral variables, companies can pay attention that the consumption behavior of halal cosmetic products is seen from consumers who purchase halal cosmetic products compared to non-halal cosmetic products.

Limitation

This study has limitations in its scope. Therefore, further researchers can add other constructs besides the constructs that have been used in this study. Future researchers are expected to examine another consumer trust by using antecedents or making it a moderating variable. In addition, further researchers can also expand the research area (not only the scope of Jakarta). Increase the number of samples according to the number of variables and indicators used and compare with the context of other halal products such as halal tourism, halal finance, or halal pharmacy.

REFERENCES

- 1) Adiba, E. M. (2019). Consumer Purchasing Behavior of Halal Cosmetics: A Study on Generations X and Y. *Journal of Islamic Monetary Economics and Finance*, 5(1), 169–192. <https://doi.org/10.21533/isjss.v2i1.52>
- 2) Ajzen, I. (1985). *From intentions to actions: A theory of planned behavior*. Springer.
- 3) Ajzen, I. (1991). The Theory of Planned Behavior Organizational Behavior. *Organizational Behavior and Human Decision Processes*, 50(2), 179–211.
- 4) Al-Mazeedi, H. M., Regenstein, J. M., & Riaz, M. N. (2013). The issue of undeclared ingredients in halal and kosher food

Consumption Behavior of Halal Cosmetic Products: The Mediating Role of Trust on The Effect of Halal Certification on Purchase Intention

- production: A focus on processing aids. *Comprehensive Reviews in Food Science and Food Safety*, 12(2), 228–233. <https://doi.org/10.1111/1541-4337.12002>
- 5) Alqudsi, S. G. (2014). Awareness and Demand for 100% Halal Supply Chain Meat Products. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 130, 167–178. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sbspro.2014.04.021>
 - 6) Ambali, A. R., & Bakar, A. N. (2013). Halāl food and products in Malaysia: People’s awareness and policy implications. *Intellectual Discourse*, 21(1), 7–32.
 - 7) Armitage, C. J., & Conner, M. (2000). Social cognition models and health behaviour: A structured review. *Psychology and Health*, 15(2), 173–189. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08870440008400299>
 - 8) Aziz, Y. A., & Chok, N. V. (2013). The Role of Halal Awareness, Halal Certification, and Marketing Components in Determining Halal Purchase Intention Among Non-Muslims in Malaysia: A Structural Equation Modeling Approach. *Journal of International Food and Agribusiness Marketing*, 25(1), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08974438.2013.723997>
 - 9) Aziz, Y. A., & Vui, C. N. (2012). The Role of Halal Awareness and Halal Certification in Influencing Non-Muslims’ Purchase Intention. *3rd International Conference on Business and Economic Research (3rd ICBER 2012) Proceeding, March*, 1819–1830.
 - 10) Bakar, A. E., Rosslee, N. N., Ariff, A. M. M., Othman, M., & Hashim, P. (2017). Consumers’ Trust and Values Towards Halal Cosmetics and Personal Care Products. *Malaysian Journal of Consumer and Family Economics*, 21–35.
 - 11) Bashir, A. M., Bayat, A., Olutuase, S. O., & Abdul Latiff, Z. A. (2019). Factors affecting consumers’ intention towards purchasing halal food in South Africa: a structural equation modelling. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 25(1), 26–48. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2018.1452813>
 - 12) BPS-Statistics of DKI Jakarta Province. (2020). *Jumlah Penduduk Provinsi DKI Jakarta Menurut Kelompok Umur dan Jenis Kelamin 2018-2019*. jakarta.bps.go.id
 - 13) DinarStandard. (2020). State of the Global Islamic Economy Report 2020/21 Thriving in Uncertainty. In *DinarStandard*.
 - 14) Faturohman, I. (2019). Faktor yang Mempengaruhi Minat Beli terhadap Makanan Halal. Studi pada Konsumen Muslim di. *Prosiding Industrial Research Workshop and National Seminar*, 10(1), 882–893.
 - 15) Ferdinand, A. (2014). *Metode Penelitian Manajemen. Pedoman Penelitian untuk Penulisan Skripsi, Tesis dan Disertasi Ilmu Manajemen* (5th ed.). Undip Press.
 - 16) Fitria, M. R., Aji, H., & Heryawan, A. Y. (2019). The Effect of Halal Awareness, Halal Certification and Halal Marketing Toward Halal Purchase Intention of Fast Food Among Muslim Millenials Generation. *Russian Journal of Agricultural and Socio-Economic Sciences*, 90(6), 76–83. <https://doi.org/10.18551/rjoas.2019-06.11>
 - 17) Ghozali, I., & Latan, H. (2015). *Partial Least Square, Konsep Teknik, dan Aplikasi menggunakan program SmartPLS 3.0 untuk Penelitian Empiris*. Undip Press.
 - 18) Handriana, T., Yulianti, P., Kurniawati, M., Arina, N. A., Aisyah, R. A., Ayu Aryani, M. G., & Wandira, R. K. (2020). Purchase behavior of millennial female generation on Halal cosmetic products. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-11-2019-0235>
 - 19) Haro, A. (2018). Determinants of Halal Cosmet-ics Purchase Intention on Indonesian Female Muslim Customer. *Journal of Entrepreneurship, Business and Economicsness and Economics*, 6(1), 78–91. www.scientificia.com
 - 20) Huda, N., Hulmansyah, H., & Rini, N. (2018). Faktor Yang Mempengaruhi Perilaku Konsumsi Produk Halal Pada Kalangan Mahasiswa Muslim. *EKUITAS (Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Keuangan)*, 2(2), 247. <https://doi.org/10.24034/j25485024.y2018.v2.i2.3944>
 - 21) Hussain, I., Rahman, S. U., Zaheer, A., & Saleem, S. (2016). Integrating factors influencing consumers’ halal products purchase: Application of theory of reasoned action. *Journal of International Food and Agribusiness Marketing*, 28(1), 35–58. <https://doi.org/10.1080/08974438.2015.1006973>
 - 22) Islam, T., & Chandrasekaran, U. (2015). Halal Marketing Growing Pie. *International Journal of Management Research and Review*, 2(12), 3938–3948.
 - 23) Ismail, I., Azlina, N., Abdullah, N., Ya, S., Zain, R. S., Asyikin, N., Noor, M., Abdullah, N., & Zain, S. (2019). *Halal Kopitiam Choices Among Young Muslim Consumers in Northern Region of Peninsular*. 13–21.
 - 24) Kadengkang, J. A., & Linarti, U. (2020). Pengukuran perilaku dan niat beli produk kosmetik halal melalui modifikasi theory of planned behavior (TPB). *Jurnal Ilmiah Psikologi Terapan*, 8(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.22219/jipt.v8i1.8769>
 - 25) Kamila, E. F. (2020). Peran Industri Halal Dalam Mengdongkrak Pertumbuhan Ekonomi Indonesia Di Era New Normal. *LIKUID: Jurnal Ekonomi Industri Halal*, 1(1).

Consumption Behavior of Halal Cosmetic Products: The Mediating Role of Trust on The Effect of Halal Certification on Purchase Intention

- 26) Khan, M. M., Asad, H., & Mehboob, I. (2017). Investigating the consumer behavior for halal endorsed products: Case of an emerging Muslim market. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 8(4), 625–641.
- 27) Kotler, P., & Keller, K. L. (2012). *Marketing Management*, 14th ed. Pearson Education, Inc.
- 28) Ma'rifat, T. N., Ismoyowati, D., & Wikarta, J. M. (2015). Analisis Perilaku Konsumen Dalam Pembelian Produk Olahan Ayam Bersertifikat Halal di Provinsi D.I Yogyakarta. *Prosiding Seminar Agroindustri Dan Lokakarya Nasional FKPT-TPI, September*, 2–3.
- 29) Majid, M. B., Sabir, I., & Ashraf, T. (2015). Consumer Purchase Intention towards Halal Cosmetics & Personal Care Products in Pakistan. *Global of Research in Business & Management*, 1(1), 45–53.
- 30) Mangkarto, M. (2005). Sertifikat halal dan pengaruhnya terhadap Kepercayaan Konsumen pada Restoran (Studi Kasus Restoran Kentucky Fried Chicken Cabang Manado). *Jurnal Ilmiah Al-Syir'ah*, 3(2).
- 31) Morgan, R. M., & Hunt, S. D. (1994). The Commitment-Trust Theory of Relationship Marketing. *Journal of Marketing*, 58(July), 20–38. <https://doi.org/10.15605/jafes.031.01.01>
- 32) Nawati, N. M., & Nasir, N. I. M. (2014). Consumers' Attitude Toward the Food Safety Certificate (FSC) in Malaysia. *Journal of Food Products Marketing*, 20(December), 140–150. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10454446.2014.921879>
- 33) Novagusda, F. N., & Deriawan. (2019). Pengaruh Pemberian Label Halal, Citra Merek dan Kualitas Multivitamin terhadap Minat Pembelian Konsumen dengan Tingkat Kepercayaan sebagai Variabel Intervening (Studi Kasus Produk Redoxon di Jabodetabek). *Jimea-Jurnal Inovasi Manajemen Ekonomi Dan Akuntansi*, 1(3), 344–359.
- 34) Nurachmi, I., & Setiawan. (2020). Pengaruh Religiusitas, Kepercayaan, dan Kepuasan terhadap Keputusan Pembelian Ulang Produk Halal. *Iqtishadia: Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 7(2), 126–137.
- 35) Nurhasanah, S., & Hariyani, H. F. (2017). Halal Purchase Intention on Processed Food. *Tazkia Islamic Finance and Business Review*, 11(2), 187–209. <https://doi.org/10.30993/tifbr.v11i2.142>
- 36) Omar, K. M., Kamariah, N., Mat, N., Imhemed, G. A., Mahdi, F., & Ali, A. (2012). *The Direct Effects of Halal Product Actual Purchase Antecedents among the International Muslim Consumers*. June, 87–92. <https://doi.org/10.5923/j.economics.20120001.20>
- 37) Putri, M. J., & Rimadias, S. (2020). Analisis aspek penentu niat konsumen dalam membeli produk halal di Indonesia (telaah pada mie ramen jepang halal). *Prosiding Seminar Nasional Akuntansi*, 1–12.
- 38) Rahman, A. A., Asrarhaghighi, E., & Rahman, S. A. (2015). Consumers and halal cosmetic products: Knowledge, religiosity, attitude and intention. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 6(1), 148–163. <https://doi.org/10.1108/JIMA-09-2013-0068>
- 39) Rajagopal, S., Ramanan, S., Visvanathan, R., & Satapathy, S. (2011). Halal certification: Implication for marketers in UAE. *Journal of Islamic Marketing*, 2(2), 138–153. <https://doi.org/10.1108/17590831111139857>
- 40) Razalli, M. R., Yusoff, R. Z., & Roslan, M. W. M. (2013). A framework of Halal certification practices for hotel industry. *Asian Social Science*, 9(11), 316–326. <https://doi.org/10.5539/ass.v9n11p316>
- 41) Rifa'i, I., Irwansyah, F. S., Sholihah, M., & Yuliawati, A. (2020). Dampak dan Pencegahan Wabah Covid-19 : Perspektif Sains dan Islam. *Jurnal Pendidikan*, 1(1), 1–10.
- 42) Romle, A. R., Udin, M. M., Seman, N. H. A., Sabu, M. A., Samsudin, M. F., & Mostapha, N. H. (2016). The Linked of Attitude , Subjective Norms, Trust , Knowledge and Intention To Use Halal Cosmetic Products Among Students : A Case of Public University in Malaysia. *International Journal of Administration and Governance*, 2(2), 15–20.
- 43) Sekaran, U., & Bougie, R. (2016). *Research Methods for Business* (Seventh ed). John Wiley & Sons Ltd.
- 44) Septianti, W., Setyawati, I., & Permana, D. (2021). The Effect of Halal Products and Brand Image on Purchasing Decisions with Purchase Interest as Mediating Variables. *European Journal of Business and Management*, 6(6), 271–277.
- 45) Setiawan, S., & Mauluddi, H. A. (2020). An Examination of Purchasing Intention towards Halal Products. *International Journal of Economics and Management Systems*, 5, 209–216.
- 46) Shafie, S., & Othman, M. N. (2006). Halal certification: an international marketing issues and challenges. *Proceeding of the International IFSAM VIIIth World Congress Pp: 28-30.*, 28–30. <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/12568103>
- 47) Shamsir, R. (2016). Store Image and Its Impact on Consumer Behavior. *ELK Asia Pacific Journal of Marketing and Retail Management*, 2(4). <https://doi.org/10.16962/EAPJMRM/issn>
- 48) Sumarni, Y. (2020). Pandemi Covid-19: Tantangan Ekonomi Dan Bisnis. *Jurnal Ekonomi Dan Perbankan Syariah*, 6(2), 46–58.
- 49) Triantoro, A., Sumarwan, U., & Hannan, S. (2020). the Development of Conceptual Model on Indonesian Consumer Behavior Towards Halal-Labeled Drugs. *Indonesian Journal of Business and Entrepreneurship*, 6(3), 256–268.

Consumption Behavior of Halal Cosmetic Products: The Mediating Role of Trust on The Effect of Halal Certification on Purchase Intention

- 50) Wibowo, M. W., Permana, D., Hanafiah, A., & Ting, H. (2020). Halal food credence : do the Malaysian non-Muslim consumers hesitate? *Journal of Islamic Marketing, May*.
- 51) Yusuf, E. W., Komaladewi, R., & Sudarma, Y. S. (2019). The Importance of Halal Product Label to Building Customer Trust. *Jurnal Ekonomi Modernisasi, 15(1)*, 58–66.
- 52) Zakaria, Z., Salim, M. R., Ahmad, Z., Haini, F., Ahmad, M., & Kamaludin, M. A. (2015). Trust as a Mediator in Determining Customers Purchase Intention of Halal Frozen Food. *International Academic Research Journal of Social Science, 1(2)*, 283–289. <http://www.iarjournal.com/wp-content/uploads/37-P283-289.pdf>